

Landowner Survey Information

Shrublands are one of many cover types (in addition to forests, wetlands, and grasslands) that provide important habitat for wildlife and are the focus of this survey. The results of this survey will lead to a better understanding of the kinds of information and incentives that would help engage landowners in creating and maintaining these habitats while also supporting ongoing land uses such as agriculture and/or timber production.

This survey is specifically referencing your property(ies) in one of the following counties: Highland, Bath, Giles, Tazewell and Smyth. If you have more than one property in these counties, please answer the questions on the sum of these properties (i.e., as if they are adjoining).

Confidentiality

- Your answers are completely confidential; your name and contact information will not be linked to your survey.
- At the end of the survey, we will ask for your preferred contact method ONLY if you would like to receive information about future and ongoing opportunities or to see the results from this survey.

General Instructions

- There are no right or wrong answers. Your best guesses are OK.
- When asked for numbers, please give us your best estimate.

Who can participate?

- The participant should be the primary person making decisions regarding land management on the property(ies) above 2000 feet and greater than 25 acres, and should be 18 years or older

How long will it take?

- It will take about 15 minutes to complete this survey.

Ownership Information

Please mark your responses clearly

1. Are you a full time resident on this property?

- Yes No

2. If not, how many months out of the year do you spend at this property?

- Less than 1 1-3 4-6 More than 6

3. How long have you or your family owned this property?

- Less than 5 years 5-10 years 10-25 years More than 25 years

4. Is any of your land under a conservation easement?

- Yes No

5. How long do you intend to continue owning your land?

- Less than 1 year 1-5 years 6-10 years More than 10 years

Existing Habitat and Past Management

6. Referring to the figure below, estimate the percentage of your property that is in each cover type?

	0%	Less than 10%	11-25%	26-50%	51-75%	More than 75%
Grassland (mostly grass with little other vegetation)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Fallow Field (mostly grass and other non-woody vegetation, with trees and/or shrubs covering less than 25%)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Shrubland (trees and/or shrubs less than 6ft tall on average and covering more than 25%)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Young Forest (trees and shrubs more than 6ft tall on average)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Old Forest (more than 20 ft tall)	<input type="checkbox"/>					

7. Have you ever harvested timber on your land?

- Yes No

8. Approximately what percentage of your land do you manage for the following activities?

	0%	Less than 10%	11-25%	26-50%	51-75%	More than 75%
Row Crop Production	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Haying	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Grazing Livestock	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Timber Production	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Hunting	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Other (i.e., vineyard, orchard, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>					

If "other", describe: _____

9. Approximately what percentage of your land do you lease for the following activities?

	0%	Less than 10%	11-25%	26-50%	51-75%	More than 75%
Row Crop Production	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Haying	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Grazing Livestock	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Timber Production	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Hunting	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Other (i.e., vineyard, orchard, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>					

If "other", describe: _____

10. Do you actively manage for wildlife habitat on your land, with the intent of maintaining/increasing/improving habitat?

- Yes (please skip to Question 11)
- No (please skip to Question 12)

11. If yes, was this management done with technical assistance from a state or federal agency (e.g., by providing a management plan or recommendations)?

- Yes (please skip to 11a)
- No (please skip to 11d)

11a. If yes, with which of the following state or federal agency(ies)?

- Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS)
- VA Department of Game and Inland Fisheries
- Agricultural Extension Office
- US Fish and Wildlife Service
- Soil and Water Conservation District
- Other: _____
- I don't know/remember
- VA Department of Forestry

11b. Did you find this to be a positive experience?

- Yes
- No

11c. Would you do it again?

- Yes
- No

11d. Was this management done with financial assistance from a state or federal program?

- Yes (please continue to 11e-11g)
- No (please skip to Question 12)

11e. If yes, from which of the following state or federal agencies did you receive financial assistance?

- Natural Resources Conservation Service - (CREP, WHIP, EQIP, CSP)
- US Fish and Wildlife Service - Partners for Fish and Wildlife
- VA Department of Game and Inland Fisheries (DMAP)
- Farm Services Agency (CRP)
- US Forest Service - Forest Legacy Program
- Other: _____
- I don't know/remember

11f. Did you find this to be a positive experience?

- Yes No

11g. Would you do it again?

- Yes No

12. Have you ever made habitat management decisions on your property to benefit wildlife?

- Yes: _____ No

Habitat Management Preferences

13. How important to you are the following with regard to your property?

	Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important
Overall appearance of your property	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The perceptions of your neighbors and fellow citizens regarding the appearance of your property	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Knowing that wildlife live on your property	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Being able to observe wildlife on your property	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Having personal hunting opportunities on your land	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Providing hunting opportunities for others on your land	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Generating revenue from hunting opportunities on your land	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Having other personal outdoor recreation opportunities on your land, for example camping, hiking, or ATV use	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Providing outdoor recreation opportunities for others on your land, for example camping, hiking, ATV use	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Generating revenue on your land (e.g. through agriculture or timber production)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Providing habitat for pollinator species (such as butterflies and honey bees)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ensuring land practices that do not impair water quality	<input type="checkbox"/>				

14. When you think of wildlife, what usually comes to mind? (Select all that apply)

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|----------------------------------|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Mammals | <input type="radio"/> Fish | <input type="radio"/> Game species (i.e., deer, turkey, grouse, etc.) |
| <input type="radio"/> Birds | <input type="radio"/> Amphibians | |
| <input type="radio"/> Reptiles | <input type="radio"/> Insects | |

15. Do you feel personally responsible for providing habitat for the wildlife on your land?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

16. Do you think your land management decisions impact wildlife and their habitat(s)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

17. How important to you are the following with regard to the land surrounding your property - that is, in the general landscape or county?

	Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important
Presence of agriculture (farming, cattle)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Presence of forested lands	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Presence of recreational opportunities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Presence of public land	<input type="checkbox"/>				

18. How likely are you to carry out the following management activities for the benefit of wildlife on your property within the next five years, either on your own or with technical/financial assistance?

	Extremely unlikely	Unlikely	Unsure	Likely	Extremely likely	N/A
Modify mowing (ex., leave some areas unmowed)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Modify grazing (ex., leave some areas ungrazed or change number of livestock/acre)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Use machinery (i.e., a bulldozer) to manage shrub cover on your field(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Use prescribed fire/controlled burning	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Use herbicides to control invasive species	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Harvest trees near a field-forest border	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Harvest trees within a forest	<input type="checkbox"/>					

19. If you had a wildlife management plan created for your land, what portion of the cost would you be willing to pay out of pocket to have it carried out, with the remainder being paid for as a cost share with a management agency?

	0%	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%	100+%
Landowner	<input type="checkbox"/>											

20. How involved would you like to be in carrying out the actual management plan on your land?

- Completely involved
- Somewhat involved
- Mostly involved
- Not at all involved

Personal Experience

21. How common is it that other landowners in your area do the following activities?

	Not at all common	Somewhat uncommon	Unsure	Somewhat common	Very common
Manage property to benefit wildlife	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Manage property for wildlife viewing	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Manage property for hunting opportunities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Manage property to produce revenue	<input type="checkbox"/>				

22. State the extent to which each of the following limits your willingness or ability to manage your land to promote wildlife habitat:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I do not have enough time	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am not financially able to	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am not financially willing to	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not think my land is suitable for management	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not have enough acreage	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not know enough about where and how to manage	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not have the appropriate skillset(s), or do not know someone with the appropriate skillset(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not have the equipment needed for management	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not have support from wildlife biologists and/or foresters	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not have support from state and/or local regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not have support from the community	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not consider wildlife management a priority for my land	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Demographics (Optional)

23. What is your age?

- Under 25
- 26-35
- 36-45
- 46-60
- 61-75
- Older than 75

24. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female

25. How would you describe yourself? (mark all that apply)

- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian
- Black or African-American
- Latino/Hispanic
- Middle Eastern or North African
- Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander
- White
- Other: _____

26. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Grade School
- High School/GED
- Technical School
- College
- Graduate School

27. Which of the following ranges best describes your household income before taxes.

- Less than \$20,000
- \$20,000 to \$34,999
- \$35,000 to \$49,999
- \$50,000 to \$74,999
- \$75,000 to \$99,999
- Over \$100,000

28. Do you hunt or trap in Virginia?

- Yes
- No (skip to question 29)

28a. If yes, which of the following game do you hunt or trap? (Select all that apply)

- Bear
- Deer
- Turkey
- Grouse/Woodcock
- Quail
- Groundhog
- Rabbit
- Squirrel
- Waterfowl
- Bobcat
- Coyote
- Fox
- Opossum
- Skunk
- Raccoon
- Other: _____

29. Do you belong to or donate money or time to any of the following environmental or conservation organizations? (Select all that apply)

- National Wild Turkey Federation
- Pheasants Forever
- Quality Deer Management Association
- Ruffed Grouse Society
- Ducks Unlimited
- The Nature Conservancy
- Audubon Society
- Sierra Club
- Quail Forever
- Quail and Upland Wildlife Federation
- Rocky Mountain Elk Foundation
- VA Deer Hunters Association
- VA Bear Hunters Association
- Trout Unlimited
- Appalachian Trail Conservancy (ATC)
- American Tree Farm System
- Other: _____

30. How do you normally receive information regarding issues related to your land? (Select all that apply)

- Newspapers
- Mail
- E-mail
- Internet (e.g., forums, social media)
- Workshops
- Radio
- Television
- Word of mouth (friends/neighbors)
- Other: _____

31. Please rank the top eight ways you prefer to receive information regarding issues related to your land, with the most preferred being number 1 and the least preferred being number 8:

- _____ Newspapers
- _____ Mail
- _____ E-mail
- _____ Internet (e.g., forums, social media)
- _____ Workshops
- _____ Radio
- _____ Television
- _____ Word of mouth (friends/neighbors)

32. Would you like to receive a summary of survey results and/or information about opportunities to enhance wildlife habitat on your property, including federal and state incentive programs?

- Yes
- No

33. Which of the following information would you like to receive?

- Survey results
- Opportunities to enhance wildlife habitat on your property
- Both

34. What is your preferred means to receive this information? We expect survey results to be available in August 2018. Your contact information will not be shared or sold:

- Email: _____
- Mail: _____
